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The Place of Genealogists in World Civilization

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***Abstract:** As one of the scientific and cultural centers of Movarounnahr, Nasaf has always attracted many researchers. In the Middle Ages, there were four schools of hadith studies in Central Asia. In the middle ages, there were central schools in the city of Nasaf, where scholars from cities and large villages visited to learn from scholars. During the time of Abu Muin Nasafi, Nasaf was a major trade and craft center, where science flourished.*

***Key words:** Nakhshab, editor, hadith, mystic, Hanafi, farsakh, mausoleum, Kalam school.*

Introduction

Being one of the cradles of human civilization, Mesopotamia has had a positive influence on the development of culture in Asian and European countries since ancient times. The study of the scientific heritage of Abu Muinan Nasafi, who played an important role in the development of theology in Mesopotamia, is of paramount importance in our country, at a time when our spiritual values are being restored.

In the 11th and 12th centuries, science and culture flourished in a number of cities in Transoxania. One of these cities was the city of Nasaf. Nasaf has always attracted many researchers as one of the scientific and cultural centers of Transoxania.

The Kashkadarya River is one of the ancient and largest rivers in the south of Uzbekistan, and people have lived around its basin since ancient times. Their way of life was closely connected with this river. This even influenced their customs to a certain extent. Over time, the names of some places in the vicinity of the Karshi oasis were forgotten or have been preserved with some changes to this day. The towns and villages of Kashkadarya, such as Navtak, Nasaf and Kesh, Kosan, Furdina, Guzar, Subakh, Kojar and Ofon, were once centers of science and culture. Among them, the city of Nasaf occupies a special place. In the 9th-12th centuries, Nasaf reached a level at which it could compete with Samarkand and Bukhara in terms of scientific and cultural development. Famous scientists, hadith

scholars and lawyers appeared in such large places as Ofuron (Obbron), Kojar, Balad (Po'lati) and Fudina.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS:

The name Nasaf is mentioned in many sources, including the works of such scholars as Istakhri, Ibn Hawqal and Maksidi. Ancient Nakhshab was pronounced as Nasaf in Arabic. Because in the local language this place was called Nakhshab in ancient times. Professor T. Nafasov emphasizes that "nakhshab" is a Sogdian word and was used to designate the river flowing through the center of the city. The famous historian P. Ravshanov called the word "Nakhshab" "a place by the water". After the Arab invasion, the name "Nasaf" came into use instead of "Nakhshab", which was preserved in subsequent periods. [1; [Page 108]

At the beginning of the 14th century, the term Karshi began to be used instead of Nakhshab or Nasaf. The palace built by Kepak Khan, a member of the Mongol ulus Chigatai, was called "Karshi" in Mongolian. This palace was built to the east of Shullektepe, on the site of the city of Nasaf, in the area of the current old city. In the Middle Ages, there were four schools of hadith in Central Asia: Merv, Bukhara, Samarkand and Nasaf. In the city of Nasaf, a major center for the study of hadith, there were schools of Ahmad ibn Muhammad Tadiyani, Hammad ibn Shakir Nasafi, Layth ibn Nasir Kojari, Abdul Momin ibn Khalaf Nasafi, and in the 11th century - Abdulaziz ibn Muhammad Nakhshabi, Muhammad ibn Ahmad Baladi, Hasan ibn Ali Hammadiya Nashabi and others. By the 8th–11th centuries, Nasaf was recognized as one of the centers of Hadith studies in the Middle East. In the Middle Ages, there were central schools in the city of Nasaf, and scholars from such cities and large villages as Pazda (Bazda), Kasbi, Kosan, Warsin, Yagna, Nowkat, Quraysh, Ofuron, Zodak, Kalosi, Muda, Sanjan, Fijkat and Maymurgh came here to study with them. Such scholars of Hadith as Kasbawi, Kasani, Gubdini, Ibsani, Pazdavi and Maymurghiti carried out their activities in the Nasaf oasis. [2; p. 36].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the 9th–12th centuries, the city of Nasaf was the largest scientific and cultural center of Maverannahr after Samarkand and Bukhara, where many scholars and experts in Hadith worked fruitfully. According to orientalist D. Rakhimzhonov, more than 3,000 hadith scholars worked in Movarunnahr in the 8th-12th centuries. Of these, more than 1,000 worked in Samarkand, more than 600 in Bukhara, more than 400 in Nasaf, more than 70 in Shash, more than 60 in Fergana, the same number in Kesh, more than 50 in Termez, more than 40 in Khorezm, and the rest in Ustrushana, Dobusia, Kushonia, and other regions. These figures clearly demonstrate the high scientific and cultural potential of the city of Nasaf in Transoxiana”.

Most of the more than 400 scientists from Nasaf came from the cities of the Nasaf oasis (Pazda, Kasbi, and Kesh). Many NASA scientists also conducted their scientific activities in the cities of Samarkand and Bukhara. The science of Hadith, like other sciences, developed in Nasafa. The great scholar of Hadith, Abu Abdullah Muhammad ibn Ismail al-Bukhari (810-870), lived for some time in the Bayan district of the city of Nasafa, collecting the necessary information for his book Al-Jami al-Sahih and making a worthy contribution to the development of the science of Hadith there. The scholar also taught his students in this city, and several famous scholars of Hadith, such as Abu Zayd Tufayl ibn Zayd (died in 892), Abu Ishaq Ibrahim ibn Maqil ibn Nasafi al-Sanjani (9th century), took lessons from him. One of the scholar's closest assistants was Jabrail ibn Awan al-Afurani from the village of Ofuron, who himself was considered an outstanding scholar of his time and one of the leaders in the science of hadith. Prominent scholars of Nasaf greeted Ismail al-Bukhari with warmth and great

respect. The residents of Nasaf considered it an honor to receive the scholar as a guest in their homes and be at his service. [2] Also, Abu Hafs al-Nasafi (died in 1142), who was born in Nasaf and studied science in Samarkand, created more than 100 works and received the title of "al-Hafiz". It is known that to achieve the level of a hafiz, it was necessary to completely memorize more than 20,000 hadiths along with their texts and commentaries. Abu Hafs also wrote a special work commenting on Ismail al-Bukhari's "Al-Jameh al-Sahih".

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In the 8th-12th centuries, Nasaf was recognized as one of the centers of Hadith studies in Movarunnahr. Since the city of Nasaf had central schools for students from all regions, scholars from cities and large villages such as Pazda (Bazda), Kasbi, Koson, Warsin, Yagna, Nowkat, Quraysh, Ofuron, Zodak, Kalosiy, Muda, Sanjan, Fijkat and Maymurgh came to this city to study. In addition, such scholars of Hadith as al-Kasbawi, al-Kasani, al-Gubdinli, al-Ibsani, al-Pazdawi and al-Maymurghi carried out fruitful scientific work in the oasis of Nasaf. The joint scientific work of three great scholars who came from the Nasaf oasis at the end of the 9th century had a fruitful influence on the city of Samarkand. The resettlement of such famous scholars as Sadrul Islam Abul Yusr Muhammad ibn Muhammad al-Pazdavi an-Nasafi (died in 1100 in Bukhara), his brother Fakhrul-Islam Abul-Hasan Ali ibn Abdulkarim al-Pazdavi an-Nasafi (died in 1089 in Kesh), Abul Mu'in an-Nasafi (1046-1114) to Samarkand significantly changed the direction of development of the Hanafi teachings in a positive direction. These scholars also contributed to the development of science in Bukhara[3]. Ibrahim ibn Maqal al-Sanjani al-Nasafi and Muhammad ibn Nasr al-Qallasiyan al-Nasafi, who were the pioneers of the interpretation of the Koran in Nasaf in the 9th century, lived long. In the 9th-10th centuries, examples of written literature began to appear in Nasaf. Abu al-Muta al-Nasafi, who lived and worked during this period, created a work in Arabic, permeated with morality and edification. Shahabiddin Nasafi (Shahabi) (10th century) was one of the famous poets of the Seljuk Empire. According to the tradition of this period, Nasafist scholars wrote in Arabic, and in the late 11th - early 12th centuries - in Persian.

Beginning in the 14th century, especially during the reign of Amir Timur, it became customary to write in the Turkic language. According to the European medieval traveler Tavernier, in all the countries of the East, Arabic was known as the language of the Koran and science, Persian as the language of poetry and elegance, and Turkish as the language of politics and war"[4]. In the late 8th - early 9th centuries, students from different countries of the Islamic world studied in the schools of hadith and jurisprudence in Nasaf. The famous historian from Bukhara Narshakhi described the flourishing of science and culture in Nasaf in the 10th - 12th centuries and mentioned one of the scientists, Najmiddin Abu Hafs Umar al-Nasafi. The name of the encyclopedist Najmiddin al-Nasafi (1068-1142), who lived in Nasaf in the middle of the 12th century, is often mentioned in the sources. He was also given the title "Maturidi". Allama wrote over 100 works on linguistics, history and jurisprudence, 10 of which have survived to this day. His work, Aqidatun Nasafi, is still taught in madrassas.

The Nasafist scholar Abul Abbas Jafar ibn Muhammad al-Mustagfiri an-Nasafi (961-1041) was one of the famous scholars of his time and wrote the work, The History of Nasaf and Kesh. Samani effectively used this scholar's work in his work, Al-Ansab, dividing the population of these two cities into 80 categories. It tells the story of 43 scholars, poets and religious figures who lived in Nasaf and Kesh in the 10th and 11th centuries. The work also provides information about 4 of the author's teachers and 2 of his students.

Abu al-Mu'in an-Nasafi (1046-1114) has been described as "the great defender of the al-Maturidiyya theological school." Allama was initially educated in his hometown of Nasaf, then moved to Samarkand and then to Bukhara. He also traveled to Damascus. He wrote *Tabsiratul adilla fil usul al-din at-tariqati iman Abu Mansur al-Maturidi* (Explanation of the Religious Scholars with Clear Proofs According to the Tariqa of Abu Mansur al-Maturidi) and *Bahrul Kalam* (Scholars of the Science of Theology). He wrote works such as *At-Tamhid li-Qawa'it Tawhid* (Introduction to the Rules of Monotheism). The scholar was a renowned scholar of his time and a prominent representative of the Hanafi school of theology in Samarkand. He was considered one of the greatest figures of his time not only as a theologian but also as a jurist and expert in methodology. As the Turkish scholar H. Otay wrote: "After the most famous scholar of the Maturidi school, Abu-l-Mu'in al-Nasafi, no one appeared like him in his way and system."

Najmiddin Umar Ibn Muhammad an-Nasafi described him in his work "Al-Qand fi-zikri ulama'i Samarkand" ("A book like candy in the remembrance of the scholars of Samarkand") as follows: "Scholars and scholars of the East and the West found pleasure in the sea of Abul Mu'in an-Nasafi's knowledge and applied the rays of light he radiated to their eyes like a parrot[5].

The scholar's students Najmiddin Umar an-Nasafi, Alauddin as-Samarkandi, Abu Bakr al-Kasani, Abul Muzaffar al-Talaqani, Ahmad al-Pazdavi (Bukhara), Abul Hasan al-Balkhi, Abul Fath al-Hilmi, Abdurashid al-Walwaliji, Mahmud as-Sagharji, Ali ibn al-Husayn as-Sakalkandi were productive and creative.

Najm al-Din al-Nasafi (1069-1142-43), a famous representative and propagandist of the Maturidi school of theology, studied in his youth with such great scholars as Abul Yusr Muhammad al-Bazdawi, al-Hasan ibn Ayda al-Malik al-Nasafi, Ismail ibn Muhammad an-Nuhi an-Nasafi, and mentored Burhan al-Din al-Marginani. He is said to have been given the al-Maturidi nisab.

One of the most famous students of Al-Maturidi in the Islamic world was al-Karim al-Pazdawi (d. 999) from the Abd al-Awm era"[6].

Sheikh Aziz al-Din Nasafi (1240-1300) was considered a theorist of perfect human knowledge[7]. Bahauddin Naqshband was taught by Qusam Sheikh of Pudina and Bahauddin Qishloqi of Mubarak.

"Aqoidi Nasafi" was used as a textbook in the madrasas of Central Asia. Also, the treatise "Hikmat al-ayn" written by Najmiddin Ali ibn Umar al-Qazwini al-Katibi an-Nasafi, a famous student of Nasir al-Din al-Tusi, alias Dabiron, who was the author of the textbook "Ar-risola ash-shamsiya fi qavoid al-mantiq", that is, the textbook on logic, was also used as a textbook in the madrasas. The textbook "Fiqh al-Kaydani" was included in the curriculum, and its author was Abdullah al-Nasafi al-Fazil al-Kaydani. Students were also taught on the basis of the book "Matlab as-Salih"[8].

CONCLUSION

So, in the 9th-12th centuries, many more such scholars and philosophers were productively active in the cultural life of the city and oasis of Nasaf, one of the largest scientific centers of Transoxiana - the second capital of Sogdiana after Samarkand. Because this potential city, located at the crossroads of the Great Silk Road, was geographically convenient and had wide opportunities, and on this blessed land, along with Islamic sciences, rare sciences related to the socio-cultural sphere, in particular secular knowledge, harmoniously developed.

Thus, in the 9th-12th centuries, many more such scholars and philosophers worked effectively in the cultural life of the city and oasis of Nasaf, one of the largest scientific centers of Transoxiana - the second capital of Sogdiana after Samarkand. Because this potential city, located at the crossroads of

the Great Silk Road, was geographically convenient and had wide opportunities, and on this blessed land, along with Islamic sciences, rare sciences related to the socio-cultural sphere, in particular secular knowledge, developed harmoniously.

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